

CYCLOPES - Fighting Cybercrime – Law Enforcement Practitioners’ Network

Deliverable 5.1

CYCLOPES Community Building Framework and Governance model

Public

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Management Summary

This deliverable 5.1 describes and marks the starting point for work package 5 about the CYCLOPES Community Building efforts. D5.1 is to set a framework and governance structure via which during the course of this 5 year project all CYCLOPES community members will work together to reach the goals, ambition and granted objectives of the project. As the CYCLOPES project is a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) and aims at establishing a Law Enforcement Practitioners' Network focusing on Fighting Cybercrime, the CYCLOPES Community building tasks are most relevant.

WP5 main focus will be to contribute to the overall CYCLOPES project Objectives 1 and 5:

- Objective 1: To form a law enforcement agencies' network across Europe, combating cybercrime
- Objective 5: To cooperate with other networks of practitioners and relevant stakeholders fighting cybercrime

This deliverable describes 8 different LEA and stakeholders Community types:

- *LEA full partners*
- *Practitioners' Forum*
- *Practitioners' Networks*
- *EU / international orgs*
- *Cybersecurity Networks*
- *Researchers' Forum*
- *Industry/SME Forum*
- *Civil Society Forum*

These Communities have in different ways of engagement and involvement which are reflected in the Framework and Governance chapters of this document. In chapter 2 an extensive overview is given with applicable Community building and engagement methods and techniques which will be used by the CYCLOPES consortium to be used during all Community building events as a way to work on all work packages and tasks results.

The CYCLOPES Community Governance model is described in chapter 3. It includes communication, collaboration and legal frameworks. In chapter 4 the upcoming deliverables are listed with 5 annual Cyclopes Community Building Reports. These reports will be based on the D5.1 framework items and report on the progress made and also take into account possible changes based on new insights or new policies. Chapter 4 also gives the major next steps for the coming 6 months (November 2021 till April 2022) as a guideline for future actions. These actions will always be closely linked and in collaboration and jointly organised with other CYCLOPES work packages to activate and promote close cooperation with all CYCLOPES Community members.

1. Introduction

The project aims to build and maintain an innovation driven network of European practitioners (law enforcement agencies) combating cybercrime. The network - in addition to identifying capability gaps and requirements and sharing best practices - focus on the ongoing dialogue with industries and academia who are delivering products and conducting research on solutions that help fight cybercrime. The consistent cooperation between LEAs, industry and academia is not only to improve the possibilities of practitioners fighting cybercrime but is to contribute to the development of European markets.

The main objective of WP5 is to establish, build and maintain cooperation with other practitioners, practitioner networks and other relevant stakeholders of CYCLOPES.

This Deliverable *D5.1 CYCLOPES Community Building Framework and Governance model*, is a result of task 5.1. This task aims to develop a framework and the governance for cooperation with external stakeholders and networks. The main activities include:

- Identification of additional stakeholders and future networks of practitioners
- Development of formal regulations needed to establish cooperation (document defining rules of cooperation, templates of agreement, NDA, etc.)
- Define the Single Point of Contact (SPoC) responsible for cooperation with particular stakeholder groups and networks
- Define the process of information exchange inside WP5, and between WP5 and the CYCLOPES Management Board.
- Establish the remit for the continual monitoring of new, relevant networks and stakeholders, which might be important for CYCLOPES (for example, networks established by future GM-01 calls).

In the following chapter the means to perform these activities will be explained.

2. CYCLOPES Community building framework

2.1. CYCLOPES Community

The CYCLOPES is a network of practitioners fighting cybercrime, establishing a dialogue with representatives of industry, academia and policymakers, but also with other practitioner networks. Therefore, it is foreseen to cooperate with external partners who can bring valuable expertise to the project. The CYCLOPES Community is divided into three main groups:

- law enforcement agencies and other practitioner institutions,
- practitioner networks relevant to the CYCLOPES domain,
- representatives of industry and academia.

CYCLOPES is associating 12 LEA practitioners as full members of the consortium and 3 LEA within the CYCLOPES LEA Community, which have already signed Letters of Support. The CYCLOPES Community strives to increase the number of practitioners associated with CYCLOPES, but also to develop useful and fruitful engagement that is mutually beneficial to all parties. Therefore, CYCLOPES aims to establish and/or maintain cooperation with:

- Selected networks of practitioners dealing with topics relevant to CYCLOPES; especially current networks: ENLETS, ENFSI, i-LEAD, i-LeaNet, EU-HYBNET and i-ProcureNet.
- EU and international organisations that are relevant stakeholders, like EC (DG HOME/CERIS), EC3, Europol's Innovation Hub, Interpol, ENISA.
- Networks and relevant stakeholders related to cybersecurity (SPARTA, ECHO, CONCORDIA, ...);
- Research (CLAIR), Industry (EOS), Ethical and Social societies and organisations.

The cooperation with the above networks and stakeholders is foreseen through interchanging information about ongoing and planned activities, particularly workshops, surveys/questionnaires, conferences, etc. as part of the activities from other work packages. The exchange of selected reports and other project outcomes relevant for both parties, plus the synchronisation of conducted actions, should help avoid duplicating and overlapping work. Moreover, cooperation is also anticipated through access (even indirect access) to communication and collaboration platforms developed or used in other networks like ENLETS and i-LEAD, iProcureNet Platform, Starir4Security Platform, CMINE Platform developed within DRIVER+ project. This approach will enable CYCLOPES to exploit the platforms in a more efficient way. The CYCLOPES partners decided that a new communication platform is not needed, based upon previous experiences in other projects. Within WP5 (and in close cooperation with WP6) it is important to define what communication information CYCLOPES will provide while using these other platforms, and, also, who can access the information related to CYCLOPES communication within these platforms.

It is also predicted that strong cooperation with the EC, particularly the Community of Users platform will allow CYCLOPES and other projects to excel; through collaborative engagement working towards a common goal.

The Community is managed by the Peter van de Crommert as CYCLOPES Community Manager (CM), appointed by WP5 leader DITSS. Other CYCLOPES partners who have established good communication channels with specific above mentioned potential CYCLOPES Community members will/can be assigned as the main focal communication point

with that specific entity. Their role is to support the community manager in achieving objective 1 and 5. WP5 will contribute to the overall CYCLOPES project Objective 1 and 5:

Objective 1: To form a law enforcement agencies' network across Europe, combating cybercrime

Objective 5: To cooperate with other networks of practitioners and relevant stakeholders fighting cybercrime

Specific members of the CYCLOPES Community are involved in project activities through participation in the practitioner workshops, annual dissemination workshops, technology scanning and research monitoring. Moreover, due to a wide range of tasks planned in WP5, CYCLOPES is in continuous contact with all Community members, to synchronise works, helping to define the CYCLOPES priority topics for the following year. Several identified members of the prospective CYCLOPES Community have signed letters of support; but, it has to be emphasised that the number of community members will increase during the project - ensuring activities are linked to the relevant audiences, and that the tasks conducted are in line with efforts of external stakeholders and networks. Moreover, this shall be in accordance with the range of practitioners' needs and requirements.

Cooperation with pivotal community members such as Europol, CEPOL, ECTEG and ENLETS shall also help the project identify the priorities at an EU level allowing the project to action work that harmonises with the developing EU strategy

2.2. Community building and engagement methods & techniques

A large number of techniques commonly used for community engagement can be put in place to engage with the envisioned CYCLOPES communities. Some of them are designed specifically to share information, while others aim to successfully involve practitioners, industry and researchers in relevant community issues like community planning, decision-making, evaluation and follow-up.

The analysis conducted of different community engagement experiences acknowledge that the most appropriate techniques for community engagement must be determined on specific circumstances, engagement objectives and goals, target audience and stakeholders as well as the available resources. **Thus, no single engagement technique will suit every issue.** In some instances, a combination of different types of techniques may be required, or specific techniques may have to be adapted to suit particular circumstances.

This report classifies techniques under five categories according to community involvement levels:

- **Inform:** to provide the CYCLOPES communities with balanced and objective information to assist them in understanding the problem, alternatives, opportunities, and/or solutions;
- **Consult:** obtain feedback on analysis, alternatives, and/or decisions;
- **Engage:** work directly with the Community members throughout the project and beyond to ensure that practitioners' concerns and aspirations are consistently understood and considered;
- **Collaborate:** partner with the CYCLOPES community members in each aspect of the decision-making process - including the development of alternative options and the

identification of the preferred 'solutions';

- **Empower:** Place final decision-making authority in the hands of the CYCLOPES community members.

In addition, we advise on classifying and choosing the right community building and engagement technique according to three categories:

- information-sharing techniques,
- consultation techniques
- active participation techniques.

These categories and the following table 1, 2 and 3 are based on TRILLION project 'D5.1 Tools and techniques for Citizens Engagement'.

Information-sharing techniques

Strategies for information sharing and transparency reinforce high levels of community engagement. Effective information sharing allows members to acquire better understanding about cybercrime related issues and motivation to participate in consultation or active participation initiatives. Successful strategies for information sharing should allow Law Enforcement Authorities to continuously acquire information about all aspects of the engagement process, monitor its progress and follow-up any issues that may arise throughout the process.

Information sharing initiatives have the advantage of quickly informing CYCLOPES Community members interest in relevant topics. In addition, information sessions can compose the big puzzle of long-term engagement process to avoid the problem of isolated stand-alone activities, which are against the principals of good community engagement process.

Before starting any process of community information sharing, it is necessary to evaluate feedbacks from other community researches. In particular, one should consider:

- what is the key message to be delivered?
- why this target group will be interested to this information?
- why is it important to LEA and other stakeholders to provide this information?

The following information sharing techniques can be used as part of the CYCLOPES community engagement activity:

Engagement techniques	Description	Strengths	Weaknesses	Suggested WPs
Online information processes	<p>Information provided via websites can be directed to different communities, translated to a number of languages to facilitate information provision to key groups, or presented on targeted sites to reach specific audiences.</p> <p>Websites can be important for providing information leading to greater transparency to government decision-making processes. Other electronic information sharing processes are also increasing in popularity including e-mails and e-newsletters.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ electronic sharing processes can reach a large number of people quickly and generally cost effectively and; ✓ changes to the information being conveyed can be made quickly and relatively cost effectively. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ not all members have reliable access to ICT resources needed to share information in this way; ✓ some groups within the community may distrust electronic processes and; ✓ a lot of resources are required in order to kept up to date online information. 	WP 6
Briefings	<p>A technique that provides key information to public authorities and decision-makers, other agencies and key stakeholders at regular intervals to assist them to stay informed about the progress of an engagement activity. Whilst often one-way in nature, by raising awareness amongst key stakeholders, briefings can lead to more effective two-way communication and the identification of issues or options not previously considered. It is particularly important to provide briefings if an engagement activity could have important implications, or if the stakeholders being briefed are likely to be impacted by decisions made as a result of the engagement activity.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ can be a useful way to build relationships with important members or communities and; ✓ often represent an effective way of ensuring members' issues are regularly identified and dealt with. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ those being briefed may have influence over the process. 	WP 5
Education and awareness programs	<p>Techniques which involve providing a specific set of often factual information, for example, how to behave in emergency situations. They can be designed to target a range of members and can support a variety of community engagement techniques and methods. Education and awareness programs can be single event or ongoing.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ very important when seeking to generate behaviour change, and; ✓ can support sustained engagement by contributing to community capacity; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ can be seen as a one-sided, non-consultative process; ✓ the "facts" being disseminated may be contested, and; ✓ can be costly to develop; 	WP 3, 4, 6 and 7
Fact sheets	<p>Fact sheets are generally brief, paper based or online documents which summarise the "facts" about a program, initiative or issue. Developing and distributing fact sheets can be a simple, timely and inexpensive way to summarise the state of the art in an engagement process. The messages contained in fact sheets should be tailored and relevant to the needs of the recipients and should avoid editorial comment.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ often an efficient way of summarising significant information for dissemination to a wide range of people and; ✓ can be developed in many languages and large text formats. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ may not be accessible to people with low literacy levels or visual impairments; ✓ distribution strategies need to be planned carefully to ensure that all of those with an interest receive copies and; ✓ facts may be contested or mistrusted. 	WP 6
Newsletters	<p>Like fact sheets, newsletters provide information about a program or issue in a paper or online format. Along with containing "facts" however, newsletters also often contain</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ if distributed on a regular basis can build community awareness and understanding; ✓ can contain 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ can be relatively expensive to develop, publish and distribute and; ✓ may not be accessible to people with low levels of literacy or visual 	WP 6

	<p>a variety of additional information including photographs, diagrams, maps and editorial comment. Typically, newsletters are targeted at members and stakeholders who are most interested in the issue. They enable agencies to provide regular information and feedback about communal issues, and the contribution made by participants and future proposed steps.</p>	<p>✓ information from a range of different stakeholders, and; ✓ can be developed in a format that appeals to the target group.</p>	<p>impairments.</p>	
Community fairs or events	<p>A community fair or event provides a fun and enjoyable venue for sharing project information and raising awareness about a particular issue. As well as distributing information, a fair provides a range of opportunities for consultation and active participation. Community fairs or events can be organised specifically as part of an engagement activity, or the engagement activities could be planned to coincide with existing community fairs or events.</p>	<p>✓ can increase the visibility and approachability of the issue; ✓ is often attended by a wide variety of people, many of whom have time to look at displays, ask questions, participate in activities, and; ✓ can support relationship building efforts.</p>	<p>✓ often attended by people beyond the immediate geographic community that may be targeted, and; ✓ can require significant staff resources to establish and maintain.</p>	WP 6
Community meetings	<p>Community public meetings are one of the most familiar methods of increasing awareness about an issue or proposal. Community meetings are generally called by the agency and have a specified time, date, venue, agenda and invitation list. Another important step is developing a strategically designed, well-crafted process agenda in advance that identifies the purpose and objectives, and the working process. The timing, format, audience mix and venues are important considerations in planning effective meetings.</p>	<p>✓ particular people and groups can be targeted and invited; ✓ is time limited; ✓ the agenda is known in advance; ✓ is relatively efficient to implement and; ✓ can be structured in a number of ways to achieve a number of outcomes.</p>	<p>✓ may not attract participants who are representative of the community; ✓ can frustrate participants as discussion is often constrained to a limited number of priorities and; ✓ is not suitable for topics around which there is significant controversy or negative opinion.</p>	WP 5 and 6

Table 1: Information sharing techniques for CYCLOPES Community building and engagement¹

Consultation techniques

Members’ consultation offers important opportunities to establish and consolidate two-way relationships between public authorities and members or communities. Initiatives for consultations can be established in parallel with other information sharing and active participation initiatives. In fact, it can be very useful to launch consultative mechanisms to maximize and diversify a wider range of opinions.

A variety of consultation techniques are available:

¹ Based on TRILLION project ‘D5.1 Tools and techniques for Citizens Engagement’

Engagement techniques	Description	Strengths	Weaknesses	Suggested WPs
Discussion groups and workshops	Facilitated discussion groups or workshops involving participants selected either randomly or to approximate the demographics of a community, can be a good way to draw out a range of views and opinions. Discussion groups and workshops usually explore a limited number of community or public-interest established issues over a brief period of time. Discussion groups tend to involve relatively open-ended dialogue whereas workshops are generally more structured activities which often combine dialogue with other strategies such as information provision.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ targets specific groups; ✓ can be structured in a number of ways to achieve a range of outcomes; ✓ harnesses community energy and knowledge to generate innovative options; ✓ can build capacity, consensus, ownership and relationships and; ✓ can be iterative or cyclical, evolving in scope over the course of a project. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ participants may not be representative; ✓ produces qualitative not quantitative information which may not be easily understood or valued and; ✓ consideration regarding the collection and analysis of qualitative data is required, and may sometimes require skilled expertise in qualitative analysis. 	WP 2, 3, 4
One-on-one interviews	One-on-one interviews involve a person who has been thoroughly briefed to pose a standard set of questions to individuals within a community. One-on-one interviews can be conducted in public places, at events, via telephone and door knocks. Although interviewing everyone in a community is generally not feasible, two or three days may allow enough time to talk with a cross-section of people. Interviewing provides important qualitative information at a level of detail that is difficult to obtain any other way.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ people will often provide much more detailed information in a one-on-one interview or discussion than they will in a public forum; ✓ is useful to gain views on sensitive or complex issues; ✓ is effective when working with people with limited literacy and; has the ability to be empowering for the participants because of the narrative response. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ expertise in qualitative analysis is required to produce a quality report; ✓ it is generally not possible to interview all community members and; ✓ can be resource intensive. 	WP 2 and 5
Open days	Open days involve providing community members with access to an office or project site that they would not normally access, for a limited period of time. They provide important learning opportunities for interested members as well providing a forum for people to raise concerns and issues and to celebrate progress. Open days can incorporate displays, printed hand-out materials as well as tours, scheduled presentations and question and answer sessions. Open days need to be well planned, advertised and suitably resourced.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ demonstrates transparency and credibility; ✓ provides concrete, first hand, learning opportunities; ✓ is time limited and; ✓ often fun for community members and staff alike. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ safety and access issues need to be considered and; ✓ can be resource intensive. 	WP 6
Polls and questionnaires	Polls generally involve posing a small number of closed questions to a range of people in order to identify community opinion. The answers sought are often "yes" or "no", or scaled responses. Polls do not always predict an outcome, rather, they provide a snapshot of public opinion at one moment in time. If people	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ permits a quantitative assessment of community opinion; ✓ responses are relatively easy to collate and; ✓ is a relatively quick and cost effective way to sample a large number of 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ requires significant effort to ensure that the sample of the population polled is representative of the broader community; ✓ does not generally provide information regarding the reasons underlying certain opinions and; ✓ does not contribute to two-way relationship building. 	WP 2, 3 and 6

	are still learning about an issue, a poll may tell you how they feel given their current level of knowledge but may not reflect how they will react once they learn more unless a deliberative component is built in to the process.		people on a variety of topics.		
Road shows	Road shows are a travelling presentation and/or display used to seek feedback about, or input into a project which potentially affects more than one community. Road shows travel to where the people are thereby reducing the distance people have to travel to have their say about a project. For road shows to be effective they should be complemented by pre-event advertising and appropriate local media exposure.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ inclusive of a number of geographic communities; ✓ ensures consistency of the information provided to different communities; ✓ can coincide with local events and; ✓ presentation of verbal and visual information provides access to a range of people. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ can be resource intensive to establish, move and staff and; ✓ outcomes can be difficult to interpret across different communities. 		WP 6
Survey research	Surveys involve posing a standard set of open and/or closed questions to a range of people. They are a popular method of collecting qualitative and quantitative information from a population at a certain point in time. Surveys can be conducted through face-to-face interviews, self-completion written forms, over the telephone, or electronically via the internet or email. Careful planning is needed for surveys to be successful. It may be helpful to seek assistance from skilled researchers in designing a survey tool to ensure that it generates useful and reliable information. Sampling strategies need to match engagement objectives.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ can be used to gain feedback from large and diverse groups of people; ✓ can often be produced and distributed in large quantities relatively cheaply; ✓ enables comparison between groups in the community, or between different stages of the process and; ✓ can provide large amounts of qualitative and quantitative data. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ many groups in the community feel they have been over-consulted by government and may react negatively to being asked to complete 'yet another survey'; ✓ may not be accessible for people with limited literacy, English as a second language or with visual impairments, and; ✓ analysing the data provided via surveys requires time, resources and skill. 		WP 3
Web-based consultation	Online chats, surveys and questionnaires enable members to contribute their views and opinions to public authorities. They also allow government to provide information and feedback to members. Online consultation is one tool which should be considered as part of a range of other consultative tools, and it can include interactive websites, Internet surveys, discussion boards, email feedback, Internet-based forums, and online chat events.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ a number of existing ICT platforms exist to support this type of engagement; ✓ can be very cost efficient; ✓ can reach a wide audience quickly; ✓ people can participate at a time and on a date that suits them and; ✓ may be appealing to people who do not wish to participate in group gatherings. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ the anonymity afforded by online processes may result in multiple responses to surveys and skewing results; ✓ resources must be allocated to ensure that questions raised are responded to in a timely manner, and; ✓ concerns about privacy and confidentiality may need to be carefully addressed to ensure participation. 		WP 5, 6, 7

Table 2: Consultation techniques for CYCLOPES Community building and engagement²

² Based on TRILLION project 'D5.1 Tools and techniques for Citizens Engagement'

Active participation techniques

Modern trends often orient towards enhanced empowerment of community members' opinions and impacts on Cybercrime policies. The idea behind is, in addition to information-sharing and consultations with members, to move beyond and involve more actively members and communities in cybercrime interest matters. A wide variety of active participation techniques are available. These initiatives need to be supported by well-designed information sharing actions and, in some other cases, can be implemented in combination with consultation actions:

Engagement techniques	Description	Strengths	Weaknesses	Suggested WPs
Action research	Action research refers to a set of research methods that enables public officials, community members and others to explore issues, difficulties and experiences in a collaborative and participative way and to identify and test solutions. The two key principles of action research are that the research processes have both an action focus and a specific focus upon developing understanding. For action research to be effective, public officials need to sensitively engage with community members, either one-on-one or in groups, and build trusting relationships within which experiences and needs can be explored. Interviews, surveys, focus groups and informal meetings can be used to support the research process.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ can be incorporated into everyday work; ✓ is inclusive – it can be used with any stakeholder group and is appropriate for socially excluded groups; ✓ is flexible and responsive – has the ability to develop/reformulate the research agenda in parallel with the project work and; ✓ supports problem solving and solution testing. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ can lose focus unless the research question is tightly defined; ✓ the qualitative data generated via action research processes may not be easily understood or valued and; ✓ participation may not be representative. 	WP 3, 7
Advisory committees	Community advisory committees made up of a representative group of stakeholders are often used to guide planning efforts over an extended period of time. In some cases, an advisory group may be established as a standing committee to provide continuing input in an important topic area of community interest.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ values a wide range of technical and local expertise and knowledge; ✓ provides an understanding of a range of perspectives, data sets and other knowledge bases in order to develop informed, agreed and integrated solutions, and; ✓ enables information and decisions to be distributed to all members. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ participants may not be representative of the various groups with relevant knowledge or skills; ✓ it can be difficult to manage the diversity of opinion, data, frameworks and other information provided via committee members and; ✓ standing committees may lose impetus or relevance. 	WP 3, 4, 5 and 7
Community reference groups	Community reference groups are made up of invited representatives from a particular community who have an interest in a given topic. Reference group members attend regular meetings, represent their group or community's views and provide input into the development, implementation and evaluation of strategies, plans, programs and	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ supports long term community engagement and relationship building; ✓ enables sharing of local knowledge and expertise; ✓ generates new ideas and provides a snapshot of likely community reaction to a particular decision or process and; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ may be too formal and structured for some community representatives; ✓ if not well-resourced and supported, community members may not be able to sustain involvement, and; ✓ difficult to ensure genuine representation. 	WP 5

	<p>services. The activities of the group can be publicised in order to generate and sustain interest and energy.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ can create intra-group rapport and trust over time. 		
Focus groups	<p>These are meetings that allow small groups of stakeholders to provide their knowledge of a project area and discuss their concerns and issues with community-based organizations, local government staff and planning consultants. Each group is focused around a specific segment of stakeholders. Focus groups are most useful in the early phases of a planning effort or the first days of a charrette to surface issues that might not otherwise come up in a public setting. They offer a way to collect information that might not be available in planning documents and hear candid perspectives from specific segments of stakeholders.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ can be used to gain the views of those who may not respond to other forms of consultation, for example, surveys, written exercises; ✓ good for in-depth exploration of people's views on an issue/service including their likes and dislikes; ✓ can be used at different stages of a consultation process from preliminary planning to the feedback stage and; ✓ can target specific groups. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ some people may feel inhibited in expressing non-consensus views; ✓ risk of "group think" and; ✓ not guaranteed to be statistically representative because of small numbers involved. 	WP 2, 3
Participatory editing	<p>Participatory editing provides members with the opportunity to shape written reports and documents, without necessarily leaving their homes. Drafts are circulated to stakeholders in hard copy or electronically for comments and feedback. An editor goes through the submitted comments and produces a revised version of the report which is then returned to the participating stakeholders for their endorsement or amendment. The process may be repeated several times until consensus is reached on the content.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ builds ownership of documents/ plans edited in this way; ✓ enables people to participate at times and on days which suit them; ✓ enables feedback to be received from a cross-section of participants from different geographic locations and; ✓ can provide the basis for a variety of other engagement techniques. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ needs sufficient time and detailed information and briefing material to ensure clarity about the requirements of participants; ✓ is difficult to ensure genuine representation and; ✓ editing may attract criticism if the final result does not adequately reflect all of the input provided. 	WP 2, 3, 5, 7
Partnerships for active participation	<p>Partnerships can be an important strategy for promoting ongoing government and community engagement. All partnerships involve an agreement to work together to achieve specific outcomes. Partnerships recognise the important contribution that each party makes to achieving an outcome. Partnerships can be formal such as the arrangements negotiated between State and local authorities and various community and industry groups to support natural resource management. Other partnerships are informal such as when a government agency and a community group agree to work together to host a consultation event. Informal</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ harnesses the resources and energy of government and community members to achieve shared outcomes; ✓ can be established in a variety of ways to achieve a variety of outcomes; ✓ is a useful to build longer term relationships and; ✓ can build the knowledge, skills and awareness of all partners. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ not all stakeholders have the resources, desire or need to partner government; ✓ no matter how well-intentioned partnerships may be, power is often not equal and in some instances it is difficult for some stakeholders to "let go" of their power; ✓ often requires extensive discussion and negotiation to agree on the nature and terms of the partnership and; ✓ requires significant commitment of resources to maintain partnerships. 	WP5

	relationships are increasingly being recognised as significant enablers of great partnership alliances.			
Future search conferences	<p>A future search conference is a participative method often used to develop a shared future vision and plan for a community. A future search conference is an effective way of developing a partnership with the community. It can be used for developing and gaining broad commitment in a strategic planning process, but depends on a strong commitment to follow through with conference outcomes.</p> <p>Future search conferences initially focus on identifying desirable futures and then concentrating on ways to achieve them. They are intensive events, usually taking place over a number of days. Participants are generally stakeholders who have power or information on the topic or who may be affected by any resulting decisions or outcomes.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ good technique for developing a vision for a community; ✓ can drive community and government action; ✓ involves a broad range of relevant stakeholders and; ✓ can develop support and consensus among stakeholders with diverse views early in the planning process. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ there may be difficulties in reaching consensus; ✓ the process may be dominated by large interest groups if not carefully planned and facilitated and; ✓ can be logistically challenging. 	WP 3, 4, 6
Imagine	<p>Imagine is a new approach to community participation based on “appreciative inquiry”. Appreciative inquiry can be used to discover, understand and foster innovations in communities by gathering positive stories and images and constructing positive interactions. Imagine focuses on exploring ways to consider “what could be” and “what is possible” by reflecting on past positive experiences. It helps participants identify a collectively desired future and vision and consider ways of translating possibilities into reality and belief into practice.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ is inclusive, all sections of the community can take part; ✓ is based on storytelling, which is familiar and fun; ✓ participants learn skills; ✓ is flexible; it can be used for a variety of topics and locations; ✓ creates a shared vision; ✓ visions are rooted in success, so should have realistic outcomes and; ✓ generates commitment and social action through willingness and ability of people to act for the common interest. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ may be seen as trendy or superficial; ✓ may create expectations which cannot be met and; ✓ participants may not be representative. 	WP 4, 6
Policy action teams	<p>Policy Action Teams are responsible for an intensive program of policy development around a particular issue e.g. ransomware attacks on SMEs. Teams are composed of 20 to 40 members representing a cross-section of government departments, as well as experts from the community, industry and tertiary education sectors. The teams bring together the expertise of those “on the ground” with that of public</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ reports and recommendations of policy action teams are grounded in first-hand practical experience and balanced by specialist knowledge; ✓ public officials, community and industry representatives work in equal; ✓ representatives from across government and from different 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ time consuming and; ✓ managing expectations can be challenging – members may be unsure whether their role is to act as an expert on a particular issue or to represent the interests of their organisation or government agency. 	WP 2

	<p>officials who have been working on the relevant issue – often in isolation. While policy action teams are encouraged to engage in “blue skies thinking, all recommendations must be evidence-based.</p>	<p>levels of government work in a collaborative manner alongside external stakeholders and other expert bodies and;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ the teams provide an opportunity for a new approach to policy development, generating energy, ideas and relationships. 	
<p>Practitioners/ officers panels</p>	<p>A practitioners panel can involve large numbers of people, often between 100 and 2000, who are selected to be representative of the population. Participants agree to take part in regular deliberations about a range of issues over a period of time. The panel members are surveyed on a regular basis on specific issues or processes to track changes in attitudes, knowledge and behaviour. Approximately one-third of the panel is replaced each year to ensure it remains representative.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ access is open to a wide range of people including minority groups; ✓ is a useful way to test new ideas and plans; ✓ is a timely and economical method once established; ✓ can undertake research at short notice; ✓ views can be tracked and measured over time; ✓ panel members develop an understanding of issues over time and; ✓ participants feel valued as long as adequate feedback is given. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ panel members may lose interest; ✓ representativeness of the panel can be compromised if panel members pull out before their term expires; ✓ may be difficult to sustain participation by panel members; ✓ can be time consuming to replace members throughout the process; ✓ resource intensive to establish; ✓ requires considerable degree of ongoing commitment from all parties involved and; <p>WP 5 and 6</p>
<p>CYCLOPES Summits - Seminars</p>	<p>A summit is a large scale, time limited event which brings together large numbers of diverse participants to consider information, engage in dialogue and to make recommendations for action. Summits are often used in the early phases of developing strategies to address particularly complex issues. They can be both a visioning and exploratory exercise. Intensive planning is required to organise a summit. Summits are interactive and can be tailored to suit a diverse group of interested community participants, key stakeholders and policy makers.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ enables open and rapid communication; ✓ supports collaborative policy making; ✓ enables multi-sectoral engagement which has the potential to develop and enhance relationships between key stakeholders and community participants; ✓ can deliver a high degree of bi-partisan and public support for key directions that emerge through summit processes and; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ requires high-level commitment and leadership for preparation and planning; ✓ effective stakeholder engagement is critical; ✓ requires effective risk management; ✓ requires significant investment in planning, engagement, coordination, management, delivery and follow up; <p>WP 6</p>
<p>Collective learning technique (also known as World café)</p>	<p>The aim of the World café is to create a discussion environment that feels like a café. World café can either be conducted online or in a public space. This method is suitable for large groups of people (has been practiced in groups of over 1,200 people). It provides a diverse group of people with an opportunity to share information and insights into</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ the method is simple in design; ✓ allows a large, diverse group of people to participate; ✓ enables information sharing on a large scale; ✓ responses do not have to be limited to written material, drawing would be equally as effective in 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ resource intensive (venues, resources, people, marketing); ✓ requires significant planning; ✓ requires a number of skilled facilitators preferably one for each table and; ✓ a significant amount of follow-up is required for further action planning. <p>WP 2, 4, 6</p>

	<p>complex issues. A number of questions are prepared and documented on a number of table. Groups are initially assigned to a table, and then given a set amount of time to respond to the questions. People are invited to talk in small, intimate groups about topics of interest. They are then asked to rotate to another table (and another question) and to add to the responses made by previous groups.</p> <p>When the final rotation has occurred, a plenary session is conducted to create a sense of connection with the wider group. This offers the whole group an opportunity to connect the overall themes or questions which are presented, and talk about the possibility for further action.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ articulating issues; ✓ allows cross-pollination of ideas across a large group of people and; ✓ is a powerful technique for creating shared knowledge of a community's issues and a subsequent sense of community. 	
<p>Community visioning</p>	<p>Creative or community visioning is an exploratory method for any number of community participants. It normally involves the facilitation of sessions in which participants are asked to close their eyes and imagine what their community looks like now, and what it could look like into the future. A scenario can be set which may provide stimuli for the visioning experience. Visualisation is the technique used and a skilled facilitator provides an atmosphere with a dialogue closely mapping out the community featured. Small group sessions can be facilitated to capture the creative thoughts of participants and follow-up planning activities begin to translate the community vision into concrete plans. There are a number of forms of community visioning, and it can be expanded to include creative arts, such as drawing, or making models out of craft materials (these can be particularly good for children).</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ large numbers and diverse participants can be involved; ✓ can be a great community building exercise creating a sense of community through the sharing of visions; ✓ explores a variety of visions for the future; ✓ focuses on possible strengths rather than issues or conflict and; ✓ is able to generate forward planning and regenerate a positive spirit and purpose. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ may create anxiety in some prospective participants and impact on recruitment for the day; ✓ requires a number of facilitators to compile and interpret the visions described; ✓ generates a lot of ideas and data for collation and analysis may be difficult and; ✓ requires careful documentation and clarity of purpose to ensure sound links to concrete outcomes. <p>WP 4, 5, 6</p>

Table 3: Active participation techniques for CYCLOPES community building and engagement ³

³ Based on TRILLION project 'D5.1 Tools and techniques for Citizens Engagement'

2.3. Different CYCLOPES communities with different approaches

CYCLOPES Communities	Who	Community techniques (Information, Consultation, Participation)	Formal and legal regulations
<i>LEA full partners</i>	<i>12 full project partners</i>	I, C, P	Grant Agreement
<i>Practitioners' Forum</i>	<i>Additional EU LEA's</i>	I, C, P	LoS, NDA, Affiliate Agreement
<i>Practitioners' Networks</i>	<i>ENLETS, ENFSI, i-LEAD, i-LeaNet, EU-HYBNET, i-ProcureNet</i>	I, C, P	LoS, NDA, Affiliate Agreement
<i>EU / international orgs</i>	<i>EC, EC3, Interpol, Europol Innovation Hub, ENISA</i>	I, C	LoS
<i>Cybersecurity Networks</i>	<i>EACTDA, SPARTA, ECHO, CONCORDIA</i>	I, C, P	LoS, NDA, Affiliate Agreement
<i>Researchers' Forum</i>	<i>CLAIR, other research institutes and universities</i>	I, C, P	LoS, NDA, Affiliate Agreement
<i>Industry/SME Forum</i>	<i>EOS, COESS, ECSO</i>	I, C, P	LoS, NDA, Affiliate Agreement
<i>Civil Society Forum</i>	<i>Ethical and Social societies organisations,....</i>	I, C	LoS

Table 4: Overview of envisioned CYCLOPES Community types

In Annex I an initial overview can be found with known and potential external CYCLOPES stakeholders including mentioning the CYCLOPES Single Point of Contacts and the formal regulation under which they should be linked to the CYCLOPES project. Since the CYCLOPES communities are mostly open for new partners this overview will be a 'living' document which needs to be update regularly (as part of D5.2, D5.3, D5.4, D5.5, D5.6).

CYCLOPES, as a European project, is focusing especially on European law enforcement agencies, industry, academia and research. But we foresee also the possibility for cooperation with institutions and organisations outside of Europe as well.

3. CYCLOPES Community Governance model

3.1. Cyclopes Community Governance

Cyclopes Community Manager

WP5 leader (DITSS), as a Cyclopes Community Manager is responsible for managing the CYCLOPES Community. The main role of the Manager is to facilitate, support and maintain the work of Single Points of Contact (SPoCs) and report their work to Project Officer and Project Board (WP Leaders). The Manager has to be prepared for every Project Board meeting and every General Assembly and present what are the areas of cooperation between CYCLOPES and external stakeholders (institutions, agencies, networks, projects, etc). Therefore, the WP5 leader has to be in permanent cooperation with SPOCs.

Single Points of Contact

All partners of CYCLOPES consortium will be responsible for cooperation with external stakeholders. To ensure efficient and effective cooperation it was decided to establish SPoCs, which will be responsible for cooperation with particular institutions / organisations / networks / projects / etc. In some cases, one consortium partner can be responsible as a SPoC only for one external partner but in many cases one consortium partner will be responsible for operating as a SPoC for a few external stakeholders in parallel. It depends on capacity of the particular Cyclopes consortium partner and on number of PMs in WP5.

It is important to underline, that a SPoCs' role is to:

- Support in synchronising Cyclopes activities with external activities in the area of fighting cybercrime. Due to the fact that many initiatives and activities are conducted in this area every year, we should avoid duplicating and overlapping with these activities. Or even more, we should discuss how we can complement other activities or how external partners can complement Cyclopes actions.
- Promote Cyclopes activities and results.
- Promote activities and results of external partners among Cyclopes consortium and Cyclopes community.

Advisory Board

CYCLOPES Advisory Board will consist representatives of most relevant stakeholders interested in providing advices and recommendations to the project. Currently it is foreseen that Advisory Board will consist of EUROPOL, CEPOL, INTERPOL, ENISA, ENFSI, ECTEG, ENLETS. Advisory Board will be managed by Project Coordinator in cooperation with PMO and Cyclopes Community Manager (WP5 leader).

3.2. Communication framework

The work and goals of CYCLOPES will be facilitated and achieved by utilising a dedicated team of Single Points of Contact for external stakeholders and partners. The SPoCs are responsible for forging connections with the previously mentioned actors; establishing and promoting interdisciplinary actions that boost the efforts of other initiatives and strengthens the linkages between the relevant stakeholders and actors in the European Cybercrime ecosystem. Furthermore, by utilising the research and activities of other WPs, the WP5 team can consider opportunities in the global theatre that support the goals, objectives and aspirations of the CYCLOPES project.

Of course the mentioned CYCLOPES community building and engagement techniques in paragraph 2.2 also serve as a communication framework or items of that framework to be described and governed within WP6.

3.3. External communication and collaboration platforms

According to the plan described at the proposal preparation phase, Cyclopes won't develop any communication and collaboration platforms. The reason for this decision is that many platforms are already developed. Therefore, the role of Cyclopes, in cooperation with SPoCs, is to discuss with external stakeholders how in an efficient way Cyclopes partners could use their platforms and tools.

3.4. Formal regulations and agreements framework

Formal regulations about confidentiality for All CYCLOPES consortium LEA partners are handled by the Grant and Consortium Agreement

For all CYCLOPES Deliverables that are marked as confidential is agreed in the Grant Agreement Table 6.1 that following Cyclopes community members: relevant LEAs and ministries within the EU and the UK, Europol, CEPOL, ECTEG and ENLETS are cleared.

For most interactions with research and Industry/SMEs, Cyclopes will deliver publicly available information, which will not include any confidential information. However, if the CYCLOPES community members decide to join a particular event/ a particular time frame this requires a NDA (Non-Disclosure Agreement), then, for this situation, a NDA will be signed. Thus, a template was created. For example, it might be necessary to be signed by organisations participating in Join Live Exercises. NDAs might also be needed for cooperation with non-EU and non-UK LEAs.

Moreover, LEAs, which would like to be strongly related to the Cyclopes project, will be encouraged to sign Letters of Cooperation for dissemination, communication and acknowledgement purposes.

Templates for NDA and Letter of Cooperation can be found in Annex I.

4. Planning and timeline

4.1. List of WP5 deliverables

The following list of WP5 deliverables have been agreed in the DoW in the CYCLOPES Grant Agreement:

Deliverable Number	Deliverable Name	Lead partner	Type	Diss. Level	Due date
D5.1	Cyclopes Community Building Framework and Governance model	DITSS	Report	PU	M6
D5.2	1 st Annual Cyclopes Community Building Report	DITSS	Report	PU	M12
D5.3	1 st Annual Cyclopes Community Building Report	DITSS	Report	PU	M24
D5.4	1 st Annual Cyclopes Community Building Report	DITSS	Report	PU	M36
D5.5	1 st Annual Cyclopes Community Building Report	DITSS	Report	PU	M48
D5.6	1 st Annual Cyclopes Community Building Report	DITSS	Report	PU	M60
D5.7	A sustainable development plan for the Cyclopes network following the project	PPHS	Report	PU	M58

Table 5: List WP5 deliverables

4.2. Relation with activities from other work packages

The CYCLOPES Community building objectives and tasks are by nature part of the collaborations and activities/events, which are integral part of all other CYCLOPES work packages.

Each CYCLOPES work package from WP1 to WP7 will have its own workshops and/or annual event. WP6 will also establish communication and dissemination channels in close cooperation with all CYCLOPES partners. WP5 will use all these events and materials to accomplish the objectives, goals, ambitions and tasks as described in the DoW.

In WP4, Task 4.3 standardization recommendations – based on needs expressed by practitioners in workshops performed by WP2 – will be discussed and elaborated with affected standardization committees and representatives from other EU-funded research projects working or having worked in the theme of the topic and where standardization was or is addressed. For the later this engagement activity will be supported by WP5.

Below you find the CYCLOPES work package structure:

Figure 1: Cyclopes Work Package Structure

4.3. Next steps

Next 6 months (November 2021 – April 2022):

- Activate/building, facilitate and maintain all CYCLOPES different communities.
- Establish communication channels with other CYCLOPES Communities (synchronize with D6.1 CYCLOPES Communication plan).
- Report results to General Assembly.

5. CYCLOPES future and sustainability

There is no doubt that significant effort in establishing and maintaining CYCLOPES Community in 5 years, will be an investment of time, energy and finances. Therefore, it is pivotal to create a sustainable and achievable continuation plan following the project's lifecycle. To support this, it is planned to develop a sustainability plan which will allow to cultivate a method for establishing maintainable cooperation after the project.

Today, we can assume that further CYCLOPES cooperation will be based on participation as part of other organisations, like ENLETS and Europol Innovation Lab, rather than creating new ones. Still, all details, including legal status, financial rules and mechanisms, mission statement, will be a part of the developed sustainability plan. The works on this task will start on month 37 of the project (May 2024) and will last to the end of the project (April 2026).

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Annex I: LoC and NDA template

Logo of institution or institution's letterhead

To the attention of:

Polish Platform for Homeland Security (PPHS)

**Coordinator of the CYCLOPES
project**

CYCLOPES Letter of Cooperation

By submitting this letter, **[name of institution]** confirms the willingness to cooperate with the CYCLOPES-project: "Fighting Cybercrime – Law Enforcement Practitioners' Network", which is granted under the Horizon 2020, topic SU-GM01-2018-2019-2020 Pan-European networks of practitioners and other actors in the field of security. The project runs for 5 years and started on May 1st 2021.

[name of institution] is willing to become a member of CYCLOPES LEA Community, and will:

- participate in workshops and other events organized by CYCLOPES project, for which we are invited and which are of interest of us;
- provide input and feedback to the project where relevant;
- help disseminate project results to relevant stakeholder;
- consider uptake of the solutions of CYCLOPES if proven successful in the project.

I understand that expenses will be covered (if needed and applicable) by the consortium budget up to a pre communicated maximum.

Sincerely,

Name:

Title/Position:

Signature:

Place, Date:

Logo of institution letterhead

To the attention of:

Polish Platform for Homeland Security (PPHS)

**Coordinator of the CYCLOPES
project**

CYCLOPES Non-Disclosure Agreement

This Non-Disclosure Agreement ("Agreement") is made by and among:

CYCLOPES project Consortium (the "Disclosing party")

AND

CYCLOPES Community member [redacted] (the "Recipient")

Collectively referred to as the "Parties" and individually as the "Party",

WHEREAS CYCLOPES is a project which aims to establish a Law Enforcement Practitioners' Network focusing on Fighting Cybercrime;

WHEREAS CYCLOPES Consortium has invited you to participate at:

[event(s)/activity(s)/.....]

WHEREAS the Disclosing Party plans to disclose certain information in connection with Confidential Information on fighting cybercrime;

WHEREAS the term "Confidential Information" shall mean the contents of the planned activities and all information furnished by the Disclosing Party to the Recipient, concerning the CYCLOPES project, including, among others without limitation, CYCLOPES related documents and files, business plans and business strategy information, processes and methodologies, specifications and technical information, software, research and developments, inventions, designs, drawings, engineering, operations, present or future products and services, assets, customer lists, market information, and any and all analyses, compilations, summaries or other documents prepared by Recipient containing or based in whole or in part on any Confidential Information obtained from the other party. Confidential Information may be furnished in tangible and intangible form including, but not limited to, writing, drawings, schematics, flow charts, computer and other electronic media, samples and verbal communications.

Confidential Information does not include information which:

a. is made publicly available on the CYCLOPES website or was available to the public prior to the receipt thereof from the Disclosing Party;

b. was known to the Recipient prior to its receipt from the Disclosing Party or was independently developed by the Recipient (such cases shall be communicated to the Disclosing Party and evidenced by Recipient's written records);

NOW THEREFORE, in consideration of the above premises, the Recipient agrees with and commits to respect the following:

1. The Recipient shall not disclose any of the Confidential Information to any person, firm or entity, without the Disclosing Party's prior written consent unless as required by law, regulation or legal process. The Recipient shall take reasonable precautions to protect Confidential Information from any unauthorised disclosure, and shall, to this end, disseminate such information internally within its organisation only on an "as needed" basis and with the agreement of the Disclosing Party. The Recipient will require from its affiliates, employees, consultants, interns, students, agents and representatives, to retain in confidence the Confidential Information, using the same degree of care as the Recipient uses to protect its own Confidential Information of a like nature.
2. The Recipient acknowledges that all right, title and interest in and to Confidential Information shall remain with the Disclosing Party; moreover, the Recipient shall not acquire any license or other property right in the Confidential Information of Disclosing Party, either expressly or by implication or otherwise.
3. The Recipient shall not use the Confidential Information for any purpose other as expressly set forth herein.
4. The Recipient acknowledges that this Agreement shall be governed by, and construed in accordance with, the Belgium laws
5. This agreement is valid and binding from the moment of subscription, for an indefinite period, unless any subsequent agreement between the Parties.

This Agreement may not be amended or modified except in a written instrument executed by each of the Parties.

IN WITNESS HEREOF, this Agreement has been fully understood and accepted by the Recipient.

Organization :

Name :

Title/Position :

Signature : _____

Place, Date :

Annex II: List of CYCLOPES Community members⁴

Cyclopes partner	Community category	Single Point of Contact WP5	Status	Formal agreement	Entry Date Cyclopes Community
<i>12 full partners</i>	Beneficiary partner		Confirmed	GA signed	1 May 2021
<i>Other EU LEA +UK</i>	Practitioners forum	DITSS	Identified	LoS, NDA, AA	
<i>ENLETS</i>	Practitioners Network	PPHS	Confirmed	LoS	1 may 2021
<i>ENFSI</i>	Practitioners Network	TBD	Identified		
<i>i-LEAD</i>	Practitioners Network	PPHS	Confirmed	LoS	1 may 2021
<i>i-LeaNet</i>	Practitioners Network	UCD or CCI?	Initiated		
<i>EU-HYBNET</i>	Practitioners Network	LAUREA	Confirmed	LoS	1 may 2021
<i>i-ProcureNet</i>	Practitioners Network	TBD	Confirmed	LoS	1 may 2021
<i>Stair4Security</i>	Practitioners Network	ASI	Confirmed	LoS	1 may 2021
<i>EC DG Home</i>	EU- international orgs	PPHS	Confirmed	GA signed	1 may 2021
<i>EC3</i>	EU- international orgs	CENTRIC	Identified		
<i>Europol Innovation Lab</i>	EU- international orgs	PPHS	Confirmed	LoS	1 may 2021
<i>ENISA</i>	EU- international orgs	TBD	Identified		
<i>Interpol</i>	EU- international orgs	TNO?	Identified		
<i>CEPOL</i>	EU- international orgs	TBD	Confirmed	LoS	1 may 2021
<i>ECTEG</i>	EU- international orgs	UCD CCI?	Confirmed	LoS	1 may 2021
<i>CEN-CENELEC</i>	EU- international orgs	ASI	Confirmed	LoS	1 may 2021
<i>EACTDA</i>	EU - other	IANUS	Identified		
<i>CyberPeace Institute</i>	Civil Society Forum	DITSS	Identified		
<i>IIP</i>	Civil Society Forum	DITSS	Identified		
<i>SPARTA</i>	Cybersecurity Networks	PPHS	Confirmed	LoS	1 may 2021
<i>ECHO</i>	Cybersecurity Networks		Confirmed	LoS	1 may 2021
<i>CONCORDIA</i>	Cybersecurity Networks		Identified		
<i>CyberSec4Europe</i>	Cybersecurity Networks		Confirmed	LoS	1 may 2021
<i>Academia and RTOs</i>	Researchers' Forum	CENTRIC			
<i>Industry and SME</i>	Industry/SME Forum	DITSS			

Representatives of Academia and RTO create "Researchers Forum".

Representatives of Industry and SME create "Industry/SME Forum".

⁴ This is initial list created in October 2021 and will be elaborated in following weeks and months